

Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers’ Effectiveness and Attitude Towards Work: Impact on Globalization

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ABSTRACT

Globally competitive mentors are the dire need of each institution around the globe to produce a competent individual; the study tackles Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization in the South Central district of Thailand Adventist Mission. One Hundred teachers were the respondents of the study.

Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers majority of them has an age range of 26-35 years old, female; single, with a bachelor degree and 6-10 years of working experience.

The level of Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work from different schools and were members of One Accord Fellowship of Thailand Adventist Mission is "Agree or High".

There is a significant relationship between Total Quality Management of Adventist teachers' attitude and effectiveness in teaching. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Quality instruments, techniques, and seminars should be afforded to teachers consistently from the different schools where they are working so that continuous quality checking can be done and maintain the high standard of the school.

Total Quality Management for Teachers in the Educational System, Job satisfaction and performance surveys must be conducted on a regular basis to address issues that may arise with instructors' attitudes. Seminars and talks on how to improve teaching skills and become a good teacher must be held.

Keywords:- Teachers' Effectiveness, and Teachers' Attitude.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

School education is the foundation or building block for further education. If we do not prioritize excellent education at the school level, the training and purpose of proficiency will fail. Teachers perception of school climate and teachers' motivational variables related to students on teachers' school satisfaction and classroom motivational climate CMC, a battery of questionnaires was validated to assess different teachers' variable based self-efficacy expectations. Cross-cultural differences were discovered in the results of both satisfaction and CMC regression analysis, as well as correlation and regression analyses (Alonso & Ruiz, 2022).

Students completing the optional level at school should have had the opportunity to submit their lives to God through individual dedication, open worship, and service and observation to others. Education provides more than just academic learning. It fosters a balanced spiritual, mental, physical, and social development of the entire individual (Rao, 2008).

White (1995) argues that teachers should be chosen from the absolute best class. They ought to be experienced individuals who are adjusted and balanced (pp. 95, 96). "They can set up the soil so that the truth may have an impact upon human hearts" (pp. 237, 238).

Another factor that makes a teacher effective in his or her job is his educational background. This is based on the study conducted by Hayman (1985), on the relationship between teacher motivation and teacher effectiveness. One hundred teachers were rated by students using a modified version of the Student Opinion of Teaching and Course. It found that teachers who possessed the highest levels of motivation and self-actualization tended to be more effective teachers.

Purser, (1986) investigated the relationship between a classification of teacher effectiveness determined by student achievement and a set of teacher variables, which included race, sex, and level of teacher certification, area of certification, years of teaching experience, and the score on the teacher evaluation summative report. The findings of his study concluded that there was no significant relationship between the performance areas (instruction, class management, interpersonal relations, and professional responsibility) and teacher effectiveness.

In 1989 Sarvis conducted a study about Comparison of attitudes of selected school teachers and principals toward the importance of teacher effectiveness characteristics in conducting teacher evaluations Teachers and principals rated 31 items on a five point Likert scale (from one = not important to five = very important). Items receiving the highest ratings were high teacher expectations, systematic classroom procedures and rules of behavior, and student practice and application of skills. This study shows that wholesome being means a lot to become more effective in performing a noble job.

The researcher hopes to determine how the teachers provide services to their students. In the meantime, they hope to investigate approaches to build up their aim of enhancing teachers' effectiveness and performance attitude towards Work.

A. Theoretical and Conceptual framework

This study is hinged in the concept of Total Quality, constructed and standardized by Sujata (1999) alike with Professor W.E. Deming's fundamentals of Total Quality Management in the 1950s. The Principles of the Adventist teachers uphold international standards to determine the teachers' effectiveness and performance attitude towards work in the schools where they are employed around the globe. The term stands for the process of shifting the focus of the organization towards a superior quality of products and services.

Conceptual Framework of Effective Teaching (adapted from Bustos[2008] Model of Critical Factors in Good Teaching and from Abulon [2014] *Basic education teachers' concept of effective teaching: Inputs to teacher education curriculum in the Philippines*)

Conceptual understanding about effective teaching was explored among basic education teachers from public schools situated in the City of Manila. Teacher-respondents from kindergarten, elementary and high school levels (N=355) were asked to respond to a questionnaire with open-ended items from which qualitative research data were gathered. Thematic analysis served as the springboard for the identification of underlying themes and core related ideas as guided by four 'a priori' major categories embodied in the study's conceptual framework. Five major themes ultimately emerged to characterize the conglomeration of conceptions of effective teaching from personality-based dispositions, teaching competence traits, content mastery and expertise, pedagogical knowledge and extension of the self. The study concluded that there was no single, predominant factor or heuristic that was identified upon which effective teaching is largely and/or solely contingent. Instead, effective teaching was viewed as a confluence of various dispositions, traits, knowledge, and skill sets. A new framework was crystallized to depict the five critical factors of effective teaching in the basic education. The resulting typical and variant core ideas of what effective teaching is, served as useful benchmarks in curriculum planning and re-designing of pre-service teacher education programs administered in teacher education institutions in the Philippines. Some implications of the findings to in-service teacher education were also established in the study (Abulon, 2014).

Figure 1 shows the schematic diagram of the study. It shows the relationship between variables. The Profile of the Teachers and the level of Teachers effectiveness and Attitude towards Work will be the independent variables and the Adventist Teachers will be the dependent variable.

B. SCHEMATIC DIAGRAM

Figure for Schematic Diagram showing the parameters of the Study

C. Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of the survey was to determine the Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization" who are attending One Accord Fellowship of the Thailand Adventist Mission, Bangkok Thailand in the school year 2019–2020.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Adventist teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age,
 - 1.2. gender,
 - 1.3. civil status,
 - 1.4. educational attainment,
 - 1.5. years in service?
2. What is the level of Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers' implementation in terms of :
 - 2.1. Teachers' Effectiveness in the workplace,
 - 2.2. Attitude towards Work?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the level of teachers' effectiveness and attitude towards work?
4. Which of the variables singly or in combination predicts the attitude towards work?

D. Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses are based on the conceptual framework and problem of the study. The thesis formulated below was subjected to testing within the 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁. There is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the level of Total Quality Management implementation in terms of Adventist Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization in the South Central District of Thailand Adventist Mission.

Ho₂. There are no variables that, singly or in combination, predict the attitude towards work.

E. Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study determined the Total Quality Management of Adventist Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization in the South Central District in the year 2020. It covered the Adventist churches within the district. The respondents of the study were Adventist teachers who were churchgoers.

The Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work Indicators include:

- Teachers' Effectiveness in the workplace.
- Attitude towards Work.

Excellent performance was based on the actual result after the study of Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization.

F. Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will specifically be address for the benefit of the following individuals and sectors.

Department of Education - the findings of the study will assist the education agency and policy makers in understanding the problems of adopting Total Quality Management in schools. As a result, in developing educational policies, they will be able to devise viable answers to these difficulties. The Education Department must realize its goal of upgrading in a timely and effective manner. The study's findings will serve as a baseline for the ministry/department to account for educational organizational quality. The data can also be capability of accredited schools. It will also establish benchmark conditions for Total Quality Management methodologies in schools.

Administrators-they become familiar with the fundamental tools, so they can take charge of the operations they oversee. School leaders will be able to comprehend and continuously enhance the process they oversee, thanks to total quality management. They will be able to predict probable success and failure lines throughout the organization's activities, which will help business, obtain ground-breaking process knowledge.

Head/Principals – will be given advice on the ideas that can be applied to raise academic performance. The research's conclusions will be useful to the quality assurance office and other existing planning, administration, and strategy creations authorities.

Teachers/Staff - with their presence and practical application, they will set the stage for teachers to acclimatize to the exceptionally globalized classroom environment. The research will help educators realize their full potential in terms of dealing with quality producing products. Teachers who are informed are more likely to be driven to speed up their job in order to improve the competency and effectiveness of the organization.

Students/Parents – as a result of identifying areas for improvement, it is envisaged that services to students, staff, parents, and other stakeholders will improve. The study's conclusions will lead to long-term service delivery.

G. Definition of Terms

Accreditations the fact of being officially recognized accepted or approved of, the act of officially recognizing, accepting or approving of something (Cambridge University Press, 2022). Quality management frameworks are widely used to prepare students for certification.

Ministry of Education is a governmental department for developing and implementing educational programs (including supervision of all public schools and public teaching programs) (Vdict.pro, 2021).

Policymakers are members of a government department, legislature, or other organization who is responsible for making new rules, laws, etc. (Cambridge University Press, 2022). A mayor, a school board, a corporation's board of directors, and the President of the country are considered as policy makers.

Educational Administrators work in schools but not as teachers. They are responsible for overseeing the administrative duties at schools from preschool through post-graduate levels. Administrators ensure teachers have the equipment and resources necessary to deliver educationally effective curriculum.

Classroom Instruction means that part of a driver education course that occurs in a classroom environment that enables a student to learn through varied instructional methods, under the direct guidance of a driver education instructor (Law Insider Inc., 2013-2022).

Teacher Effectiveness is the ability to utilize approaches, strategies, connection to students, and a particular set of attitudes that lead to improved student learning and achievement.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter discusses the related literature and studies that provide direct reference in conceptualizing the research study. The Department of Education has made a promise to give an expansive education and holistic/moral arrangement for kids, youth, and youthful grown-ups within the setting of the humane perspective.

A. Teachers Profile

Scholars' comments on Teachers Quality Performance were derived from a big percent coming from the teachers' profile. Teachers' perception towards Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) Assessment at program level and relationship with the teachers' demographic factors and it was studied by Tun and Ye (2019). Two Secondary High Schools in Laiza and Mai Ja Yang Townships, Kachin State, Myanmar, were studied. Data were analyzed by frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). Findings showed that there was no significant difference between male teachers and female teachers' perception towards internal quality assurance system according to gender.

Educators organize their learning which is an important aspect of educational research this was examined (Chue, 2022); as a result it seeks to introduce an alternative method based on a Rasch Model that may be better suited to understanding educators' learning profiles. The data fit the Rasch Model perfectly, and categories for all items were clearly ordered, according to the analysis. Cluster analysis of these ability measures revealed four groups of students with varying degrees of deep surface learning approaches. Comparisons of age and gender across clusters revealed that students with a high, deep, and low surface approach were significantly older than others.

Article 36 paragraph 1 of Indonesian Law No. 14 of 2005 concerns teachers and lecturers, as cited by (Darmawan, Yusuf and Suseno, et al., 2021), teachers who have achieved, are exceptionally dedicated, and/or work in a special area are entitled to receive awards under Indonesian law. The goal of this research is to create a decision support system using the profile matching method. This study's findings take the form of recommendations for exemplary teachers who meet the criteria established by the relevant parties.

There is agreement on the importance of including computer science in official curricula. This discipline will not be widely taught until there are enough trained teachers who can effectively lead the class. Their study determined whether a single teacher training program can be effective in teaching CS content and specific pedagogy to teachers with very diverse backgrounds. There are significant differences in their self-perceptions of teaching career opportunities. Their conclusion was that providing their training to a diverse range of profiles may be effective in promoting CS content. However, if the goal is to increase teachers' confidence in teaching CS subject, a program that focuses on a more limited set of profiles would be a better strategy (Czemerinski, Scasso, & Schapachnik, 2020).

Gallagher (2016) explores the profiles of 252 fourth and fifth grade teachers' mathematics instructional practices and the influence of those practices and the teachers' mathematical knowledge for teaching on student mathematics growth. The results indicated that there were four meaningful and distinct profiles of teachers' practices: weak practices, lots of errors, developing practices, and strong practices. In the final model, there were statistically significant differences in growth between students in classes of teachers with developing and weak practices.

An analysis of the psychosocial profile of pre-service teachers was conducted, and the psychosocial aspects, such as resilience, helped to address the imbalance they often experience in their daily lives. Resilience is able to significantly predict students' mental health directly, and it predicts all personality components assessed in students. Of all the personality factors examined, only neuroticism was found to be predictive of mental health (Garcia, Augusto, & Pérez, et al. 2022).

Job satisfaction and stress are important factors in mathematics instruction quality. Using latent profile analysis, this study investigates their combined influence on mathematics teachers' dialogic instruction. Teachers with low job satisfaction and high stress were less likely to use dialogic instruction than teachers with other characteristics. The study discovered that teacher job satisfaction was linked to self-efficacy and leadership support (Hwang, 2022).

The adaptation of the teachers to the digital age, the integration of their digital skills into the learning and teaching processes, and their digital awareness, competencies, and fluency constitute an important problem that is within the scope of lifelong learning. The aim of the present study is to examine the digital profiles of pre-service teachers within the framework of universal education principles and online learning theories during the pandemic period. Their digital awareness, competence, and fluency levels are going to be highlighted, and the concepts are going to be discussed in the light of current developments that are under the effects of the pandemic (Karakuş & Kılıç, 2022).

Laitinen (2022) expanded on the latent profiles of work burnout and engagement in health education teachers. The greater the demands placed on teachers, the more likely they were to fit the burnout profile. Pedagogical self-efficacy, social belonging, and social support all increased the likelihood of belonging to the engaged profile. Determining job and personal resources, as well as job demands, may be beneficial to the well-being of health education teachers.

The authors of the Education 4.0 concept, Ramirez, Loaiza, and Zúñiga et al. (2021), proposed a flexible combination of digital literacy, critical thinking, and problem solving in education environments. The purpose of this study was to identify the teaching profile required in new undergraduate programs at a higher education institution in Ecuador. The findings defined the profile of a specialized professional with competencies in innovation, complex problem-solving, entrepreneurship, international perspective, leadership, and connection to societal needs.

B. Total Quality Management

The perception of teachers of Total Quality Management in relation to teaching strategies and practices was examined. Twenty teachers were interviewed regarding their use of Total Quality Management and Learning Lab methodologies in their teaching activities. All teachers agreed that the tactics improved their teaching and that positive attitudes, teamwork, and activity variety resulted in student achievement (Elliot, 1997).

Herguner (1995) evaluates Total Quality Management (TQM) as a management philosophy and finds its relevance, adequacy, and relative success. The theory focuses on an organization's shared values, style, staff, and skills rather than its system, structure, strategy. Though the PDCA cycle played a role in the project for both teachers and researchers involved in this study of organizational development, the thesis is not concerned with the teaching and learning process.

Improving the teaching quality of colleges has become the common and only theme of all the colleges and universities all over the world. Our colleges should promptly change the traditional concept and build a new, scientific, rational, and effective teaching quality monitoring system. Total Quality Management is applied in the teaching quality monitoring system. This paper is unique in that, in addition to my regular university work, I investigated the existing teaching quality monitoring system in School A. (Tian, 2012).

Secondary vocational education is an essential component of the modern Chinese educational system. In recent years, secondary vocational schools have faced numerous challenges in moving forward against the backdrop of China's accession to the WTO and its own concerns. It is apparent that the teaching has deteriorated significantly. The schools should be conducted efficiently in accordance with the total quality management of the teaching system (XU, 2008).

Erdem (2021) addresses the evaluations of administrators and teachers working in primary schools on sustainable strategic planning practices in schools. The study followed a quantitative research approach and was limited to primary schools in Ankara, Turkey. The findings of the study and their implications are expected to benefit the development of primary schools.

Johnson (1998) also compared and analyzed educators' assessments of the level of implementation of Total Quality Management principles in selected South Carolina and Georgia schools. The researcher gathered data and analyzed teachers' assessments by using a causal-comparative method that included the administering of the Total Quality Management Survey (developed by Dr. Dennis Nielsen, 1996). The Malcolm Baldrige National Award Program and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences were used to collect data. Training in Total Quality Management principles had a positive effect on the implementation of these principles in schools. There were significant differences between the assessments of trained, somewhat trained, and untrained educators in regard to the level of implementation of TQMs. The difference between assessments of administrators regarding the levels of implementation was not significant.

The T.Q.M. approach has proved adequate only in coping with issues such as leadership, culture, and relationships, which could have been addressed anyway through the paradigms of school improvement and effectiveness. Apparently, another managerial approach should be sought which may more appropriately address these issues (Kovrigaro, 2002).

C. Teacher Effectiveness in the Workplace

The teachers fighting spirit in performing the teaching jobs affected by his/her surroundings. A mixed-method sequential study was set out by Maniglia (2017) to find out how well teachers and administrators in a suburban New Jersey high school understood the traits and actions of teachers who scored highly on the six criteria of the Strong Teacher Effectiveness Performance Evaluating System. Additionally, this study investigated whether there was a correlation between students' growth scores and effectiveness evaluations for teacher practice.

In the academic year 2013–2014, Pennsylvania implemented the Teacher Effectiveness System to assess instructors based on a variety of factors. There hasn't been any study on how this method is perceived by teachers and principals since it first began. This survey aimed to determine how valuable administrators and teachers thought the Pennsylvania teacher's evaluation system was. The research involved three different school districts in southeast Pennsylvania. According to research, administrators and instructors enjoy constant professional input on their teaching practices (Batchelor, 2021).

Grant (2020) mentioned about two leadership styles have dominated the literature: instructional leadership and transformational leadership. No study could be found quantitatively integrating principal practices from these styles in ways that simultaneously predicted teacher effectiveness and teacher morale. Therefore, this study sought to better understand the complex relationships between principal practices, teacher effectiveness, and teacher morale. First, this study synthesized Meta analyses of principal effects for studies produced between 1978 and 2008 and presented a unique empirically grounded integration framework summarizing principal effects for student achievement and teacher morale. Second, the study used this framework to explore four research questions. An online survey was utilized to collect data from a snowball sample of middle school teachers. The study compared teacher perspectives on principal practices, teacher effectiveness, and teacher morale in low and high-poverty middle schools in California. Second, this study analyzed the relationships between twelve leadership dimensions and five teacher outcomes. Next, the

study tested the predictive effects of school-level variables and twelve leadership dimensions. Finally, this study explored if and how diverse leadership practices could be integrated to predict burned out, ineffective, overextended, or engaged teachers. The results of this study demonstrated no significant difference between the perspectives of teachers in low- or high-poverty middle schools. Correlations were stronger between dimensions of instructional leadership and dimensions of teacher effectiveness. Laissez-faire leadership is correlated with increased emotional exhaustion and depersonalization experienced by teachers. Regression analysis found that each dimension of leadership predicted one or more dimensions of teacher effectiveness and teacher morale, confirming the effort to integrate leadership practices.

Morris (2017) conducted a quantitative study to compare measures of teacher effectiveness across two Tennessee teacher evaluation methods. The Teacher Instructional Growth for Effective and Results Model (TIGER) and the Tennessee Educator Acceleration Model (TEAM) were the two teacher evaluation approaches that were compared. Final observation scores and individual value-added growth scores were utilized as indicators of instructor efficacy. The correlation between observation scores and growth scores was also examined for the two different assessment methodologies. There were related null hypotheses for each of the four primary study issues. The results showed statistically significant positive correlation between observation scores for both. The results demonstrate a greater interaction between TIGER teachers and students than TEAM teachers.

In a world that always looks for discoveries to enhance education an educational agency is bound to hire a teachers who were highly trained for a specific job. A bachelor's degree, state certification, and matter knowledge are required for the highly qualified teacher title. The research presented a thorough conceptual model and definition of teacher effectiveness. A multiple case study using mixed techniques with three objectives was carried out. First, the study investigated and described practices in NCLB highly certified instructors. Second, the effectiveness of instructors' classroom methods was investigated and reported through observations of lesson planning, management, and delivery. Third, the study investigated teacher and principal opinions of the traits and experiences of effective teachers. Data on teacher qualifications, characteristics, and classroom methods were submitted by principals and teachers. A teacher survey, principal and teacher interviews, teacher observations, and document reviews were used to collect data. According to the findings, teacher effectiveness was defined holistically by the combination of instructor credentials, personal qualities, and classroom performance (Lewis, 2011).

Hayman (1985) explored the relationship between teacher motivation and teacher effectiveness. Students rated 100 teachers using a modified version of Part 1 of W. J. McKeachie's Student Opinion of Teaching and Course. Teachers with highest degrees of motivation and self-actualization were shown to be more effective teachers.

Surveys of teachers were also utilized to examine how they felt about the evaluation process. According to the findings, value-added teacher evaluations did not consistently result in higher student mean test scores. Contrarily, under value-added teacher evaluations, students' mean test score growth regularly increased at a statistically significant level. Additionally, a student's previous year's accomplishment score had a negative connection with student achievement score growth, indicating that as a student's previous year's achievement score dropped, achievement growth rose. The correlation between principal-based observations and teacher effectiveness evaluations was also quite weak. Finally, instructors usually had a poor opinion of the new evaluation method. These findings, which were in line with the previous studies, have repercussions for legislators, parents, and administrators (Michalek, 2014).

From 1983 to 2019, this genealogical dissertation Newland (2021) tracks the growth of teacher effectiveness as a normative discourse in educational policy. Enabling conditions have emerged, such as the perception of a failed educational system in the United States and the prevalence of a market-based approach to education. While the covid 19 pandemic, the parental testing opt-out campaign, and counter-narratives to a nation at risk acted as discontinuities, the debate on teacher effectiveness continued. Despite popular belief

that art educators reside outside the jurisdiction of educational policy, this dissertation examines the impact of teacher effectiveness rhetoric on the subject of art education.

Another strand of taking into account teacher's effectiveness is clearly, less motivated teachers are less productive and less likely to give their all, notwithstanding their secondary school teaching experience. This article investigates the impact of the minimum wage and timely salary payment on teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools using equity theory, valence expectancy theory, and the two-factor theory. The study's sample was collected from 20 selected public secondary schools in Oyo State's Ibadan North local government area. It has been demonstrated that many instructors are unsatisfied with their minimum wage payments, and that timely salary payment affects teachers' effectiveness. as a result, the study proposed that the government reconsider the current minimum salary, making it more appealing to encourage teachers and therefore directly improving teachers' effectiveness (Adekambi & Ukpere, 2021).

According to Mosconi (2022), teachers are essential in assisting students' learning. Making sure that pupils of color and those from poor socioeconomic backgrounds have access to competent instructors will help to overcome the achievement gap. This quantitative correlation study's goal was to examine the connection between teachers' overall success in the classroom and their knowledge, perceptions, and use of culturally sensitive methods. This gives strong support for the need for teachers to have improved training and assistance in implementing culturally sensitive teaching strategies in their classrooms.

These findings should guide lawmakers, policymakers, district and school administrators, and educational preparation programs in developing stronger frameworks to assist teachers in putting these approaches into practice in a way that best meets the needs of students.

Brown (2021) said, as schools make the shift to standards-based grading, teachers are required to adopt new practices. Understanding the impact such a change has on teachers' sense of self-efficacy and effectiveness in the classroom is critical so teachers can be appropriately supported.

This study reveals means for improving teachers' self-efficiency through staff development and collaboration, as well as provides insights for leaders planning such transitions.

D. Teacher Attitude towards Work

Organizational change in education is considered a constant as new methods, means, philosophies, and legislation are presented as well as personnel, materials, students, and student needs to vary on an annual, or even daily, basis.

Through qualitative participatory action research based on Vygotsky's work on the relationship between cognition, social interactions, and the environment as well as Bandura's research on self-regulation relates to the behavioral and emotional regulation.

Hathon (1989) studied the effects of statewide teacher evaluation system pilot program on academic achievement, attitudes, and conduct. The measure was used by teachers to examine how they felt the assessment system affected their performance, attitudes, and conduct. Statistical analysis was performed on the data using the computer program Statistical Package for Social Science. To determine the relative importance of the research variables, descriptive statistics were generated. According to the investigation, the assessment system had a big impact on how well instructors performed and how they behaved.

Hoffman (2006) conducted a study using a survey questionnaire and the Scale of Teachers' Attitudes toward Inclusion (STATIC) assessment. This study explores the inclusion attitudes of secondary school teachers. However, a variety of factors, such as the attitudes of instructors in general education and special education towards inclusion, affect how well this technique works. The study's conclusions showed that special education instructors had views toward inclusion that were noticeably more favorable than those of general education teachers. The results also show that when instructors had taken more special education

courses and had been working at their present school for longer periods of time, their views toward inclusion were more positive.

Another research aimed to alter general education instructors' attitudes and views about inclusion. The study's foundation included on-site inspections at the charter school, questionnaires, and interviews. The characteristics that affect general education teachers' attitudes toward inclusion were the subjects of the study's research questions. The findings of this study indicate that the number of students with disabilities in general education classrooms as well as the instructors' lack of special education training, knowledge, and experience have an impact on their views toward inclusion (Sprowl-Loftis, 2013).

Some schools have started rearranging their learning spaces in response to the ongoing demand put on American public schools. Freiberg (2014), find out that the association between academic achievement and attitudes toward departmentalization among primary students and teachers in the research. A fourth-and-fifth grade classroom in an elementary school used a departmentalized form of education. According to the findings, primary school pupils who switched classrooms frequently felt positively about their instructors and about themselves as social beings at school.

Alshawi & Alshumaimeri (2017) also found out that the use of an electronic portfolio is a potential strategy for turning teachers into reflective practitioners who can adjust to changing contexts, criteria, and technology. The participants were doing practical training in schools while also e-portfolioing their knowledge and experiences. This study examines the connections between the effectiveness of EFL student instructors' instruction, the caliber of their electronic portfolios, and their attitudes toward utilizing them. The findings demonstrated both a high degree of e-portfolio ability among EFL student teachers and favorable sentiments concerning their use. The outcomes also showed a statistically significant positive correlation between the effectiveness of the EFL student instructors' instruction and the standard of their electronic portfolios.

One strategy to encourage teachers to perform better and thereby raise student achievement is compensation reform, sometimes known as pay-for-performance. In the study of Forand (2012), pay-for-performance views and attitudes among teachers in the East Providence Public School District are investigated. Additionally, pay-for-performance attitudes and beliefs are compared to employee data, such as work title, years of employment, and grade taught. If East Providence school district members decide to look into other compensation methods, the knowledge gained on teachers' attitudes and views will add to the increasing body of study on these systems.

The paper of (Alonso & Ruiz, 2022) seeks to study the potential effect of teachers' perception of school climate and teachers' motivational variables related to students on teachers' satisfaction with school, and classroom motivational climate (CMC). Confirmatory factor analyses showed the adequacy of each questionnaire structure. Results on correlation and regression analyses showed that teachers' self-efficacy expectancies are the main factors potentially influencing their satisfaction with schools. In both regression analyses – satisfaction and CMC –, cross-cultural differences were found.

Puto (2022) investigated the use of technology by EFL preservice teachers in managing and teaching speaking skills online during emergency remote teaching in Indonesia. It used an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design to implement a single case study approach. The findings revealed that, while the pre-service teachers used a variety of technology tools, they frequently used WhatsApp, YouTube, and Google Forms for classroom management and teaching.

Quality assurance strategies focused on external supervisory roles, principals' supervisory responsibilities, exposure to training programs, and teacher qualification. According to the findings, effective supervision in schools by both external supervisors and principals does not directly improve teachers' performance; moreover, the government should improve teachers' working conditions, particularly their pay (Lawal, 2021).

According to Nickl, Huber, & Sommerhoff, et al. (2022), assessing students on the spot is an important but difficult task for teachers. Because of technological advances, this training can now take place in authentic learning environments such as video-based simulations. It is necessary to determine how cognitive and motivational learner characteristics influence situative learning experiences in order to comprehend the learning process in such simulations. The findings could serve as a foundation for future simulation research focusing on adaptive and individual support.

Rasheed (2022) evaluated the quality of training programs for teachers of students with disabilities in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in light of recent trends. The findings revealed flaws in the training teachers on their roles and responsibilities, standards for effective use of educational skills, and the development of values and ideas. The study suggested that the Ministry of Education focus on developing a strategic plan to improve teacher training programs.

Xiao, Li, & Song et al. (2022) propose a three-module cross-teacher training framework that significantly improves traditional semi-supervised learning approaches. The core is a module that can simultaneously reduce peer network coupling and error accumulation between teacher and student networks. The high-level module can transfer high-quality knowledge from labeled to unlabeled data and promote class separation in feature space. On benchmark datasets, our framework outperformed state-of-the-art methods in experiments.

E. Teachers' Impact on Globalization

Mentoring practices represent a space for knowledge reconfiguration, a locus of collective knowledge construction, and territories where student-teachers can mobilize and exercise their agency. Mentors have constructed ways to fracture traditional and hegemonic logics of seeing knowledge and the self in teacher education (Aguirre, E., & Ubaque, D., 2022).

Multinational corporations (MNCs) such as Intel, Microsoft, and Cisco began investing in education in Costa Rica starting in 1994. New economic demand for Costa Rica has led to policy changes for the education system. With the continued support of the Ministry of Education, MNCs, and school site leaders, the hope is for further growth (Arora, A. 2014).

According to Behera, J., and Sahoo, D. (2022), a negative (negative) change in globalization leads to a decline (increase) in human development in the long run. In the short run, a positive shock in globalization with one lag has a positive impact on human development. It is suggested that India has to promote both globalization and ICT judiciously.

Another situation discovered is "hate speech." It has become a social problem that needs to be addressed urgently. Debates of this type should be channeled into a democratic debate and the definition of shared objectives. The development of counter-speeches and alternative narratives based on human rights should be tackled (Castellvi, J., Massip, M., & Gonzales, G.A., et al. 2022).

Clegg, S.A. (2007) attempts to investigate the nature of supply teaching and how it differs from being a primary school class teacher. The data, which included interviews with head teachers and supply teachers, led me to three key areas that had an impact on the work of supply teachers.

Psychological and pedagogical research sought to investigate student's unique characteristics and how to incorporate them into the educational process. The internal motivation of future IT specialist to continue education and training, internal motivation for professional activity as a software engineer, and reflective skills are the focus of this study (Krashenninik, I.V., Koniukhov, S.L., Osadcha, K.P., et al. 2022).

Teachers are feeling more stressed and anxious as they try to keep up with the numerous curriculum changes that have occurred since the beginning of democracy in 1994. The data revealed that mathematics teachers are ill-equipped to meet the needs of socio-culturally diverse students (Safura Meer, and Michael Moos, V. W. 2022).

Ten Chinese animations about ethnic were chosen, watched, and rated by two groups of people from all over the world. The number of likes, comments, and willingness to share the animations were used to gauge participant's interest in and engagement with watching them. The findings may be useful to animators, travel agencies, politicians, and the legislative and executive branches (Sun, Q. 2022).

Westernization through English teaching is problematic in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), according to Waterkeyn, T. (2021), protectionist stances on Islamic and cultural roots counter international strategies. The findings show that English is perceived more positively and used more diversity than previous studies have claimed.

According to Yang, J. (2022), the study of contemporary art is one of the main means of implementing aesthetic education in China. This discipline allows a student to develop a system of spiritual values, reveal talents, and acquire skills needed for professional growth. In the course of the study, a plan and structure for the website, which would contain audio and video materials, graphic editors, and a conference system for students and teachers, were developed. An innovative classification of the contemporary art movements was made in accordance with the tools and methods of creating art works. The styles of contemporary art were divided into groups: painting, sculpture/architecture, photography, cybernetic art, literature, optical art, theatrical art, mass culture, and hybrid art. An experiment was conducted to determine the level of effectiveness of different methods of teaching contemporary art in China.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the research method, locale of the study, the sampling procedure, and the respondents of the study, the instrumentation, and the statistical technique used.

A. Research Design

The study used the descriptive-correlational survey method to describe the profile of the teachers, level of Adventist Teachers' Effectiveness and Attitude towards work within One Accord Fellowship in Central Zone 2 district of Thailand Adventist Mission, Bangkok Thailand. The relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables were determined.

B. Subjects of the Study

The participants of the study included the Adventist teachers in different schools who are members of One Accord Fellowship in Central Zone 2 of Thailand Adventist Mission, Bangkok Thailand. There were 100 Adventist teachers in that District of Thailand Adventist Mission.

Complete enumeration was used to determine the sample size.

C. The Research Locale

The study was conducted in the One Accord Fellowship of the Central Zone-2 under Thailand Adventist Mission, known for its strategic location, numerous factories and Malls make it the heart of business in the Southern part of Bangkok, Thailand. Bangkok is the capital of the Kingdom and it is a prosperous city, i.e., having a wide economic influence on the metropolis and the rest of the region; it has a land area of 1,569 km².

D. Research Instrumentation

The instrument of the study was adopted from Total Quality, constructed and standardized by Sujata (1999). This self-study instrument has been devised specifically for Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work and incorporates key areas, such as teaching and learning and services to students that are lacking in the generic checklists.

In this self-study there were two instrument checklist, first is for Teachers Effectiveness in the workplace, there are 47 quality indicators under: I have full authority on the subject I am teaching, besides my teaching subject, I have the ability to teach other needed subjects like current like current events, general knowledge etc., I advise the students to solve their problems according to their needs, I give due opportunities to the students for proper motivation, I use more rewards and lesser punishment in the classroom for achievement of desired aims, A lengthy curriculum does not allow a teacher to use teaching aids or black board, I am well prepared when I come for teaching, I always appreciate student's opinions and demands, I admit my mistakes, pointed out by students willingly, I respect the head of institution as our senior most member, I listen patiently, even the irrelevant, question of the student and try to solve them, I co-operate willingly in t5he daily assignment of the school, A teacher cannot behave equally to all the students, A teacher cannot behave equally to all the students, I have respectfully with all guardians without discriminating caste, social status and economics status etc., One cannot be always punctual, It is very cumbersome to check all homework notebooks regularly, I co-operate with the guardian to solve the problem of student for their proper development according the right opportunity, I take interested in co-curricular activities organized in the school, I prepare the student to in co-curricular activities according to their abilities and interested, I prepare lesson plan regularly, I am fully conversantly with the instructional objectives of the lesson, I select proper teaching aids before hands, I am creative, I feel accountable, I have adjustment capacity, I communicate the subject matter clearly before the students, I developed student's interesting the lesson, I make proper use of the blackboard, I give attention to each student individually, I

have proper rapport with my students, I use material aids in the teaching, I use needed remedial measure in teaching, After finishing the lesson, I review it, I try my best to solve pupils problem in the classroom, I have emotional stability, I control the class confidently, I have complete knowledge of basis of educational psychology, I have complete knowledge of basis of individual differences, I always try to use contemporary educational devices in the teaching, While teaching, I use examples from daily life situations, I am smart, active and cheerful in the school, I give corporal punishment to the students, I am missionary zeal, I am disciplined, I ensure that the students understand me when I am teaching.

The second instrument checklist was for Teachers Attitude towards Work, there are 45 indicators under it: Teaching skills is highly technical, Good teaching keeps the record of position holders, Teaching helps in making a person, more and more progressive, Teaching helps in developing one's social circle, By teaching through the principle of "Learning by doing" the teacher develops dignity of labor in the student, Classroom teaching strengthens the desire to learn, Good teaching helps in fulfilling instructional objectives, Good relationships between teacher and a student is essential for teaching, Teaching of us an opportunity to enjoy the company of intellectual people, Good teaching demands effective communication abilities, Classroom teaching makes the teacher more creative, Teaching at primary school does not help the teacher in being research minded, Teaching at primary stage is less prestigious than teaching at high school, Teaching gives an opportunity to peal superior in company of other, Teaching creates a sense of co-operation among students, A teacher has to be well prepared to teach satisfactorily, Weak students cannot progress through classroom teaching only, Teaching should be mixed up with humor to make learning more interesting, Trained teachers are more confident than undertrained ones in solving students' problem, It is good that now a days attitude of students is given importance, Teachers should be authoritative in the classroom to teach effectively, There are more chances of promotion for more experienced teachers, Teaching as a professional always has a bright future, Teaching as a carrier is not respected in society, Teaching develops noble sentiments, Teaching is an art as well as a science, Students should be given freedom to think, There should be a distance between teachers and students for better classroom teaching, Teaching opens the door to compete for other professions, People never look down upon good teachers, Teaching work isolates one from higher social circle, Teaching makes a teacher tired and frustrated, A person can serve humanity better by teaching in and outside the school, Good teaching develops freedom talents and special abilities of the student, Teaching should be a participatory venture in the classroom, It is a curse to remain in a teaching, Teaching does not determine the moral standard of a nation, Teaching leaves a person from darkness to light, Use of blackboard is an essential component of good teaching, Teaching should give freedom to the students to learn according to their own pace, Remedial teaching is an essential component of effective school climate, Bright and talented teachers are always creative in teaching, No occupation is better than teaching, Teaching is not a good vehicle to serve the humanity, Teaching develops personality and character.

These have been weighted to show their relative importance in the quality process. The highest weighted areas are effective teaching and learning and leadership. Teaching and Leadership are of crucial importance because numerous studies have shown that strong teaching and leadership are the key features of high performing educational institutions. Excellent teachers inspire their colleagues and ensure that there is a drive for quality improvement. In those establishments where student success is high, those working in them and particularly their management have a clear understanding of standards and the actions necessary to achieve them. Try out of the questionnaire was done to ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Central Zone-2 Coordinator and the district pastor in the South Central district of Thailand Adventist Mission through a request letter to conduct research to Adventist Teachers of South Central district under their supervisory. Upon the approval of the request, the questionnaires were distributed to the Adventist teachers in the South Central district of Thailand Adventist Mission. The researcher explained the general instructions before administering the questionnaires to the respondents.

F. Scoring Procedure

The scale and scoring below were used to determine the extent of Total Quality Management implementation in the present study.

<i>Scale Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.51–5.00	5	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.51-4.50	4	Agree	High
2.52-3.50	3	Neutral	Moderate
1.51-2.50	2	Disagree	Low
1.00-1.50	1	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

G. Statistical Techniques

Responses to the questionnaires and the data which were collected were summarized, translated, and analyzed. The descriptive statistics were employed for the summary and analysis of data including frequencies, percentages, and means.

The relationship between the independent variables was established using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis.

Regression analysis was used to determine variables that predict the Attitude towards Work.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

A. Demographic Profile of the Adventist Teachers

The demographic profile of the Adventist Teachers is presented in Table 1.

CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age		
25 years and below	17	17.0
26 - 35 years old	53	53.0
36 - 45 years old	22	22.0
46 – 55 years old	7	7.0
56 – 65 years old	1	1.0
Gender		
Male	32	32.0
Female	68	68.0
Civil Status		
Single	63	63.0
Married	35	35.0
Separated		0.0
Widowed	2	2.0
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	94	94.0
Masteral Degree	5	5.0
Doctoral Degree	1	1.0
Years in Service		
5 years and below	31	31.0
6 – 10 years	47	47.0
11 – 15 years	13	13.0
16 – 20 years	5	5.0
21 – 25 years		0.0
26 – 30 years	1	1.0
31 years and above	3	3.0

Table 1: Demographic profile of the Adventist Teachers

There were 53 (53.0%) teachers who have an age range of 26-35 years old followed with 22 (22.0%) teachers who are 36-45 years old, 17 (17.0%) 25 years and below, 7 (5.00%) 46–55 years old and 1 (2.00%) of them are 56–65 years old; Majority of them were female (100, 68.00%). There are 35 (38.00%) married; 63 (63.0%) are single and 2 (2.0%) are widowed. For the educational attainment, Out of 100 teachers, 94 of them are bachelor's degree holders; 5 attained Master's degrees, and 1 doctoral degree holder. Almost half of the teachers or 47 of them worked for 6 - 10 years, followed with 31 teachers who are in service for 5 years and below, 13 teachers for 11-15 years, 5 teachers for 16-20 years, 3 teachers for 31 years and above and 1 teacher who worked 26-30 years.

B. Level of Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work of Adventist Teachers

There were 2 scales in Level of Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work of Adventist Teachers in the South Central District of Thailand Adventist Mission. The quality indicators were: Teachers' Effectiveness in the workplace and Teachers Attitude towards Work

Table 2 showed the quality indicators in terms of Teachers Effectiveness in the workplace, there were 47 constructs.

Quality Indicators	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. I have full authority on the subject I am teaching.	4.38	Agree
2. Besides my teaching subject. I can teach other needed subjects like current events, general knowledge, etc.	4.14	Agree
3. I advise the students to solve their problems according to their needs.	4.10	Agree
4. I give due opportunities to the students for proper motivation.	4.36	Agree
5. I use more rewards and lesser punishment in the classroom for the achievement of the desired aims.	4.11	Agree
6. A lengthy curriculum does not allow a teacher to use teaching aids or blackboard.	3.22	Undecided
7. I am well prepared when I come to teaching.	4.26	Agree
8. I always appreciate the student's opinions and demands.	4.35	Agree
9. I admit my mistakes, pointed out by students willingly.	4.36	Agree
10. I respect the head of the institution as our senior-most member.	4.51	Strongly Agree
11. I listen patiently, even the irrelevant, question of the student, and try to solve them.	4.36	Agree
12. I co-operate willingly in the daily assignment of the school.	4.36	Agree
13. A teacher cannot behave equally to all the students.	3.76	Agree
14. I have enough self-confidence.	4.08	Agree
15. I keep a friendly and brotherly relationship with my teacher colleagues.	4.42	Agree
16. I have respectfully with all guardians without discriminating caste, social status, and economic status, etc.	4.42	Agree
17. One cannot be always punctual.	3.68	Agree
18. It is very cumbersome to check all homework notebooks regularly.	3.75	Agree
19. I co-operate with the guardian to solve the problem of students for their proper development according to the right opportunity.	4.26	Agree
20. I take interested in co-curricular activities organized in the school.	4.33	Agree
21. I prepare the student for co-curricular activities according to their abilities and interests.	4.19	Agree
22. I prepare lesson plan regularly.	3.98	Agree
23. I am fully conversant with the instructional objectives of the lesson.	4.07	Agree
24. I select proper teaching aids before hands.	4.25	Agree
25. I am creative.	4.16	Agree
26. I feel accountable.	4.80	Agree
27. I have adjustment capacity.	4.30	Agree
28. I communicate the subject matter clearly before the students.	4.32	Agree
29. I developed a student's interest in the lesson.	4.33	Agree
30. I make proper use of the blackboard.	4.21	Agree
31. I give attention to each student individually.	4.28	Agree
32. I have a proper rapport with my students.	4.30	Agree
33. I use material aids in the teaching.	4.31	Agree

34. I use needed remedial measures in teaching.	4.08	Agree
35. After finishing the lesson, I review it.	4.30	Agree
36. I try my best to solve the pupil's problem in the classroom.	4.22	Agree
37. I have emotional stability.	4.09	Agree
38. I control the class confidently.	4.15	Agree
39. I have complete knowledge of the basis of educational psychology.	3.99	Agree
40. I have complete knowledge of the basis of individual differences.	3.99	Agree
41. I always try to use contemporary educational devices in the teaching.	4.09	Agree
42. While teaching, I use examples from daily life situations.	4.29	Agree
43. I am smart, active, and cheerful in the school.	4.16	Agree
44. I give corporal punishment to the students.	3.25	Undecided
45. I am a missionary zeal.	4.02	Agree
46. I am disciplined.	4.21	Agree
47. I ensure that the students understand me when I am teaching.	4.47	Agree
Overall Mean	4.17	Agree

Table 2: Teachers Effectiveness

Legend:

<i>Rating</i>	<i>Scale Range</i>	<i>Description</i>
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Undecided
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

It can be observed that most of the indicators were perceived as Agreed. There are top 5 indicators 2 of them are found strongly agree: I feel accountable (4.80); I respect the head of Institution as our senior-most member (4.51); I ensure that the students understand me when I am teaching (4.47); There are two indicators that rank 4 in the top five: I keep friendly and brotherly relationship with my teacher colleagues and I have respectfully with all guardians without discriminating caste, social status, and economic status, etc. (4.42); I have full authority on the subject I am teaching (4.38). While there were indicators which the teachers were undecided of: A lengthy curriculum does not allow a teacher to use teaching aids or blackboard. (3.22); I give corporal punishment to the students (3.25). The overall mean is 4.17 which is described as Agree.

The findings implied that when it comes to punishment there are schools that allow foreign teachers to impose it inside the classroom for the sake of discipline with the presence of the local teachers and the teachers cannot perform well is he/she is given broad topics to teach of given a load more than the length of time to teach the matter.

Table 3 showed the quality indicators in terms of Teachers Attitude towards Work; there were 45 constructs.

Quality Indicators	MEAN	DESCRIPTIVE RATING
1. Teaching skills are highly technical.	3.95	Agree
2. Good teaching keeps the record of position holders.	4.10	Agree
3. Teaching helps in making a person, more and more progressive.	4.37	Agree
4. Teaching helps in developing one's social circle.	4.44	Agree
5. By teaching through the principle of "Learning by doing" the teacher develops the dignity of labor in the student.	4.33	Agree
6. Classroom teaching strengthens the desire to learn.	4.36	Agree
7. Good teaching helps in fulfilling instructional objectives.	4.46	Agree
8. Good relationships between teacher and a student is essential for teaching	4.59	Strongly Agree
9. Teaching of us an opportunity to enjoy the company of intelligent people.	4.46	Agree
10. Good teaching demands effective communication abilities.	4.29	Agree
11. Classroom teaching makes the teacher more creative.	4.39	Agree
12. Teaching at primary school does not help the teacher in being research-minded.	3.80	Agree
13. Teaching at the primary stage is less prestigious than teaching at high school.	2.80	Undecided
14. Teaching allows peeling superior in the company of others.	3.00	Undecided
15. Teaching creates a sense of co-operation among students.	3.71	Agree
16. A teacher has to be well prepared to teach satisfactorily.	4.51	Strongly Agree
17. Weak students cannot progress through classroom teaching only.	4.23	Agree
18. Teaching should be mixed up with humor to make learning more interesting.	4.02	Agree
19. Trained teachers are more confident than undertrained ones in solving students' problems.	4.20	Agree
20. It is good that now a day's attitude of students is given importance.	4.15	Agree
21. Teachers should be authoritative in the classroom to teach effectively.	4.24	Agree
22. There are more chances of promotion for more experienced teachers.	3.95	Agree
23. Teaching as a professional always has a bright future.	4.14	Agree
24. Teaching as a carrier is not respected in society.	3.70	Agree
25. Teaching develops noble sentiments.	3.37	Undecided
26. Teaching is an art as well as a science.	4.29	Agree
27. Students should be given the freedom to think.	4.50	Agree
28. There should be a distance between teachers and students for better classroom teaching.	4.32	Agree
29. Teaching opens the door to compete for other professions.	3.64	Agree
30. People never look down upon good teachers.	3.95	Agree
31. Teaching work isolates one from a higher social circle.	3.70	Agree
32. Teaching makes a teacher tired and frustrated.	3.17	Undecided
33. A person can serve humanity better by teaching in and outside the school.	3.60	Agree
34. Good teaching develops freedom talents and special abilities of the student.	4.18	Agree
35. Teaching should be a participatory venture in the classroom.	4.33	Agree
36. It is a curse to remain in teaching.	3.49	Undecided
37. Teaching does not determine the moral standard of a nation.	2.59	Undecided
38. Teaching leaves a person from darkness to light.	3.47	Undecided

39. The use of blackboard is an essential component of good teaching.	3.71	Agree
40. Teaching should give freedom to the students to learn according to their own pace.	3.97	Agree
41. Remedial teaching is an essential component of an effective school climate.	4.04	Agree
42. Bright and talented teachers are always creative in teaching.	3.90	Agree
43. No occupation is better than teaching.	3.42	Agree
44. Teaching is not a good vehicle to serve the humanity.	2.47	Disagree
45. Teaching develops personality and character.	4.34	Agree
Overall Mean	3.96	Agree

Table 3: Teachers Attitude towards Work

Legend:

Scales	Range	Descriptive Rating
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Undecided
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

The Adventist Teachers' Attitude towards Work mostly described as Agree. The top 5 constructs include: Two indicators rank strongly agree; Good relationships between teacher and a student are essential for teaching (4.59), A teacher has to be well prepared to teach satisfactorily (4.51) followed by agreed results; Students should be given the freedom to think (4.50), Two rank number four; Good teaching helps in fulfilling instructional objectives and Teaching of us an opportunity to enjoy the company of intelligent people (4.46), Teaching helps in developing one's social circle (4.44). Seven constructs are described as "Undecided" these are; It is a curse to remain in teaching (3.49), Teachings leaves a person from darkness to light (3.47), Teaching develops noble sentiments (3.37), Teaching makes a teacher tired and frustrated (3.17), Teaching allows peeling superior in the company of other (3.00), Teaching at primary stage is less prestigious than teaching at high school (2.80), Teaching does not determine the moral standard of a nation (2.59). There is only one construct that was described as "Disagree"; (2.47) Teaching is not a good vehicle to serve the humanity. The overall mean is 3.79 which is described as Agree.

The findings implied that the Adventist Teachers Attitude Towards Work in One Accord Fellowship in Central Zone 2 district of Thailand Adventist Mission were undecided to It is a curse to remain in teaching, Teachings leaves a person from darkness to light, Teaching develops noble sentiments, Teaching makes a teacher tired and frustrated, Teaching allows peeling superior in the company of other, Teaching at primary stage is less prestigious than teaching at high school, Teaching does not determine the moral standard of a nation.

The level of Effectiveness and Attitude toward Work of Adventist Teachers in One Accord Fellowship in the Central Zone 2 district of Thailand Adventist Mission is shown in Table 4. It can be seen that the overall mean is 4.06 which is described as "Agree".

The findings implied that Adventist Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work is High' in their respective schools but there are few of the indicators that were not fully applied.

Quality Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
Teachers Effectiveness in the workplace.	4.17	Agree	High
Teacher Performance towards teaching	3.96	Agree	High
Overall Mean	4.06	Agree	High

Table 4: Summary of the level Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work of Adventist Teachers

Legend:

Rating	Scale Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	High
3	2.51-3.50	Undecided	Moderate
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low
1	1.00- 1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Effective and successful total quality management implementation can be a powerful vehicle by which organizations can achieve excellence in business performance (Ater, 2013). Implementation of total quality management enables organizations to continuously improve the quality of their products and services to meet and satisfy changing customer needs. This takes place within a dynamic, changing environment brought about by competition and demand for higher quality.

Pheng and Jasmine (2014) added, Effective management is an important and indispensable factor for the successful implementation. Commitment from top management assists the workforce to adopt a clear direction for functioning and working. Other contributory factors regarding implementation are: resources; employee satisfaction and needs; training; suitable organizational culture; favorable environment; subordinates' cooperation; effective curriculum; effective planning, etc., which are essential to the successful implementation of Total Quality Management.

The correlation between variables was shown in Table 5. It can be gleaned that among the independent variables presented, the profile of the teachers such as age ($r=.080$, $p\text{-value}= .599$); gender ($r= -.217$, $p\text{-value}= .152$); civil status ($r= .092$, $p\text{-value}= .548$); educational attainment ($r= .105$, $p\text{-value}= .494$); and years in service ($r=.039$, $p\text{-value}= .801$) do not have significant relationship towards the attitude towards work. Since the $p\text{-value}$ is greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

On the other hand, the level of TQM of Adventist Teachers Effectiveness ($r= .328$, $p\text{-value}= .028$) has a significant relationship with the attitude towards work. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Variables	Coefficient Correlation (r)	Sig.	Remarks
Profile of Teachers			
Age	.080	.559	Not significant
Gender	-.217	.152	Not significant
Civil Status	.092	.548	Not significant
Educational Attainment	.105	.494	Not significant
Years in service	.039	.801	Not significant
Level of			
Teachers Effectiveness	.328*	.028	Significant

Table 5: Correlation between the profile and level of Adventist Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The findings implied that teachers’ profiles do not affect the attitude while teachers’ effectiveness affects attitude towards work. This means that when teacher effectiveness increased, the performance will also increase regardless of their profile.

The result is supported by Rao and Kummer (2007) who pointed out that performance is the extent to which an employee accomplishes the tasks that make up his or her job Performance can also be defined as a record of outcomes produced during a specific job, over a specific time. Similarly, Performance refers to the amount of effort, initiative, and absenteeism, maintenance of standards, and commitment displayed by individuals while performing the job tasks.

C. Variables that Best Predict Teachers Attitude towards Work

Table 6 illustrates the stepwise multiple regression analysis on variables under the profile and teachers’ effectiveness. As presented in table 5, it can be gleaned that among the variables, there are only two (2) variables that were found to be statistically significant predictors of teachers’ attitude towards work. These are the following: gender (Beta= -.355) and effectiveness (Beta= .541).

Independent Variables	UNSTANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS		STANDARDIZED COEFFICIENTS	T	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.356	1.368		-.260	.796
Gender	-.395	.172	-.355	-2.292	.028
Effectiveness	.990	.283	.541	3.496	.001

Table 6: Regression Analysis of Teachers attitude towards work

Note: $R^2 = .292$ $R = .540$ $F\text{-ratio} = 2.607,$ $Prob. = .032$

As indicated in the F -value of 2.607 with the corresponding p -value of 0.032, it implies that the regression model is significant. The coefficient of determination (R) is .540, which indicates that 54% in the variation of teachers’ attitude could be attributed to the gender and TQM effectiveness, while 46% were attributed to the other variables not included in this study.

Therefore, the null hypothesis states that “there is no variable that predicts teachers’ attitude towards work” is rejected. Hence, the regression equation would be:

$$\hat{Y} = -3.56 + -.395X_1 + .990X_2$$

Where:

\hat{Y} = Teachers’ Attitude towards work

X_1 = gender

X_2 = effectiveness

The findings confirmed with Gupta (2008) investigated the correlates of effectiveness and ineffectiveness in teacher’s teaching. He found job performance and financial support to be significantly influencing effective teaching.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter contains the summary of findings, the conclusions extracted from the given findings, and the recommendations based on the conclusions.

A. Summary

The study determined the Teachers Effectiveness and Attitude towards Work: Impact on Globalization in One Accord Fellowship in the Central Zone 2 in the year 2020. It covered the Adventist churches within the district. 100 Adventist teachers who were the churchgoers are the respondents of the study.

The study used the descriptive-correlational survey method. The descriptive statistics were employed for the summary and analysis of data including frequencies, percentages, and means. The relationship between the independent variables was established using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. Regression analysis was used to determine variables that predict the teachers' attitude towards work.

Findings revealed that the majority of the teachers were 26-35 years old, female, single, with a bachelor degree and 6-10 years of working experience.

The teacher's effectiveness in school they are working as an overall mean of 4.17 which is described as "agree". Attitude towards teaching has an overall mean of 3.96 and described as "agree".

The teacher's effectiveness with $r = .328$ and p -value of $.028$ had a significant relationship with the attitude of the teachers.

Gender and teachers' effectiveness were predictors of teachers' attitude.

B. Conclusions

The following are drawn from the findings mentioned above:

Findings revealed that the majority of the teachers are middle adults, female, single, they are bachelor degree holders and mostly served in schools for 6-10 years.

The teachers' effectiveness is "High." The attitude towards teaching is also "High."

There is a significant relationship between teachers' attitude and effectiveness in teaching. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Lastly, gender and effectiveness in teaching predict the attitude of teachers. The null hypothesis is rejected.

C. Recommendation

Based on the conclusions given, the following are then advanced for consideration.

Adventist teachers are encouraged to pursue master and doctoral degrees for their professional growth. The school where the teacher is employed must evaluate their teachers on the implementation of Total Quality Management in the educational system. In this way, possible difficulties and concerns will be addressed to enhanced commitment and effectiveness among the teachers.

Job satisfaction and performance survey must be done regularly to address problems that will arise regarding the performance attitude of the teachers.

Conduct of seminars and lectures on how to enhance the teaching strategies, and how to be an effective teacher must be done; the strategies that can be learned through these workshops will help the teacher attained high job satisfaction and performance.

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